

CEOTRES: A PROJECT FOR THE PHOTOVOLTAIC GENERATION OF SOLAR FUELS

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ABSTRACT: CEOTRES is a project funded by the Regional Government of the Comunidad de Madrid that aims to explore ideas in the frontier of knowledge for the application of photovoltaics to the generation of solar fuels. In this framework, in this work we: a) describe a thermodynamic analysis that can assist to screen which solar fuel production could be economically feasible from basic principles as well as to estimate the minimum amount of energy required to capture CO₂ from air; b) we review an electrochemical process, based mainly on the use of dehydrogenases and nicotine adenine dinucleotide, that could be used to convert CO₂ into methanol and c) an electrochemical process suitable for capturing CO₂ from ambient air.

1 INTRODUCTION

The photovoltaic production of solar fuels faces several challenges. One of these challenges lies in the development of suitable electrolyzers, a problem that becomes more relevant when the electrochemical reduction of CO₂ is considered. In contrast to water electrolysis, where only hydrogen and oxygen are produced, in the CO₂ Reduction Reaction (CO₂RR) multiple products can be produced (CO, HCOOH, HCHO, CH₄...) [1] which is inconvenient. In this respect, in section 2, we shall review the operation of one of the systems proposed to reduce selectively CO₂ into methanol. The system is based on the use of dehydrogenases enzymes and nicotine adenine dinucleotides.

Another challenge relies on the obtention of CO₂ itself. In this respect CO₂, can be mainly obtained from industrial point sources or being directly captured from air (DAC) [2], [3]. In CEOTRES we focus our attention in DAC systems and in this work, in section 3, we shall review the operation of a system proposed by Wang et al. [4] based on the use of K₂SO₄ and capable of capturing CO₂ from air using electrochemistry.

Finally, in section 4, we shall describe the fundamentals of a thermodynamic analysis that allows screening what organic compounds are cost competitive from the perspective of cost associated to the energy necessary to produce them as well as to estimate the minimum amount of energy that would be required for capturing 1 metric ton (abbreviated by “t” in this work and corresponding to 1000 Kg) of CO₂ from air.

2 A METHOD FOR THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PRODUCTION OF METHANOL

One of the processes being investigated in our project to achieve the reduction of CO₂ into methanol can be described by the global reaction:

The idealized setup for carrying out this process is illustrated in Fig. 1. It consists of one anode and 3 cathodes (connected in parallel). We shall start the description of the operation of this electrolyzer at the anode. Here, 6

molecules of water decompose into 12 protons and 3 oxygen molecules releasing 12 electrons to the external electric circuit:

The PV generator drives these electrons from the anode towards the three cathodes at the time it raises their electrostatic potential energy thanks to the energy captured from the sun. Among the 12 electrons, each cathode takes 4 electrons.

Cathode 1 is composed of an electrode and an enzyme called W-FDH (tungsten-formate dehydrogenase) capable of catalysing CO₂ into formate (COOH⁻) [5]. With 4 electrons and 2 of the protons that were also released at the anode, 2 CO₂ molecules can be catalyzed to produce 2 formate molecules:

Cathode 2 also receives 4 electrons. Another enzyme, called diaphorase, is attached to this electrode. The solution contains also a redox cofactor called nicotine adenine dinucleotide (NAD). The following reaction occurs then at this cathode:

A second enzyme, called formaldehyde-dehydrogenase recycles NADH back into NAD⁺ at the time it takes 4 protons to transform the formate produced in cathode 1 into formaldehyde (HCOH):

Notice this reaction also regenerates 2 molecules of water, to be subtracted from the initial six water molecules that were initially decomposed at the anode, producing as a result the net balance of 4 water molecules consumed appearing in Eq. (1).

Cathode 3 is also attached to the diaphorase enzyme, where the same reaction (4) than in cathode 2 takes place, and consuming the remaining 4 electrons. In this cathode, an enzyme called methanol-dehydrogenase (MDH) is attached what regenerates the NADH produced by the

diaphorase at the time it finally transforms formaldehyde into methanol [6]:

Notice that Eq. (3), plus twice Eq. (4) plus Eqs. (5) and (6) give a net result of 12 protons used, which equals the 12 protons generated in the anode by means of reaction (12).

As for the coupling of the photovoltaic converters to the electrolyzers, we consider that indirect coupling, through DC/DC converters and maximum power point trackers is best suited than direct coupling. Although direct coupling has the advantage of avoiding losses in the DC/DC converter, we think that these losses will be largely compensated by the indirect coupling thanks to the preservation of the maximum power operation point of the solar converters, even if solar irradiance changes, and to the possibility of precisely matching in practice the operation potential required by the electrolyzers. Moreover, this is particularly important for the methanol example being illustrated here where cathode *a* and cathode *b* will require different potentials to operate optimally.

3 A METHOD FOR THE ELECTROCHEMICAL CO₂ DIRECT AIR CAPTURE.

Capturing CO₂ from industrial sources has the advantage it is highly concentrated, but it has the disadvantage that it can contain contaminants that will have to be removed before feeding the electrochemical solar fuel production systems. These contaminants are specific of the industrial process so that the design of the purifying process will likely have to be specifically adapted to the industrial process involved.

On the other hand, supplying CO₂ from direct air capture (DAC) can provide CO₂ almost free of these contaminants. Also, DAC could allow for the design of a universal process, suitable for being used at all locations of the Earth, perhaps with only minor modifications. However, this will have to be done at the cost of a higher energy consumption associated to the need of extracting the more diluted CO₂ from air.

There are also electrochemical processes allowing capturing CO₂ from air. One example has been provided by Wang et al. [4], whose results have been emphasized in the review in [3] as a process with an energy consumption lower than 400 kJ/mol, which is considered a target to be achieved for these technologies.

The process starts (Fig. 2) with an aqueous solution of K₂SO₄ (chamber 1) sandwiched by two selective membranes, one cation exchange membrane, such as Naffion 551, allowing K⁺ ions passing through towards chamber 3, and an anion exchange membrane, such as AMI-7001, allowing SO₄⁼ ions to pass through chamber 2, where the anode is located. At this anode, 2 water molecules are oxidized releasing 4 protons to the aqueous solution, one oxygen molecule to the air and 4 electrons to the electric circuit:

The SO₄⁼ and H⁺ ions diffuse then from chamber 2 to chamber 4.

The solar generator raises the energy of the electrons released at the anode and pumps them to the cathode located in chamber 3. At this cathode, these electrons reduce H₂O to produce hydrogen and OH⁻ ions:

The OH⁻ and K⁺ ions from chamber 1 combine with CO₂ to produce K₂CO₃ or KHCO₃.

K₂CO₃ and KHCO₃ diffuse towards chamber 4 where they encounter H⁺ and SO₄⁼ ions that diffused from chamber 2 and the following reactions, releasing CO₂, takes place:

The resulting K₂SO₄ can be then recycled into chamber 1. It is interesting to note that this process, as in water electrolysis, produces, simultaneously to CO₂ capture, H₂, Eq. (8) and O₂, Eq. (7).

4 THERMODYNAMICS AND COST ANALYSIS

Thermodynamics allows to calculate the minimum amount of energy that would be required to produce a given solar fuel starting from concentrated CO₂ and H₂O only. We shall illustrate this type of calculation taking methanol (CH₃OH) as an example.

Let us assume that we initially have a system consisting of 3 mol of CO₂ and 6 mol of H₂O in thermodynamic equilibrium with a pressure and thermal reservoir at 1 atm and 298 K (that is, the atmosphere). The system is then attached to a work source (which nature does not need to be specified at this stage, but that in our case it consists of an ideal PV system providing electric work) and, together with the reservoir, it is made to evolve reversibly, and therefore quasi-statically, to an state in which 3 mol of methanol and 6 mol of O₂ are present, as illustrated by Eq. (1). That the system *plus* the reservoir evolve reversibly means that, considered both together, they do not increase their total entropy, although entropy can be exchanged between both. On the other hand, we recall that work sources, by definition, do not supply entropy to the system they are attached to.

In this context, thermodynamics [7] states that the minimum amount of work, Δ*W*, that the work source needs to supply to undertake the above process per mol of CH₃OH is given by the increment in Gibb's free energy:

$$\Delta W = \Delta_f G^0[\text{CH}_3\text{OH}(\text{l})] + 3/2\Delta_f G^0[\text{O}_2(\text{g})] - \Delta_f G^0[\text{CO}_2(\text{g})] - 2\Delta_f G^0[\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})] \quad (13)$$

where Δ_fG⁰ is the Gibbs energy of formation of the compound indicated in square brackets. The resulting figure, taking data from [8], for methanol is Δ*W*=702.47 kJmol⁻¹.

Table I: Electricity cost per metric ton (t) of product assuming an electricity price of 35 €/MWh⁻¹ and that the minimum amount of energy allowed by thermodynamics is used to synthesize the product from CO₂ and H₂O. The extra cost assuming CO₂ is captured from air in ideal conditions is also indicated. For the calculations the following data have been assumed: Δ_fG⁰ = -394.359 kJmol⁻¹ for CO₂(g); Δ_fG⁰ = -237.19 kJmol⁻¹ for H₂O(l); Δ_fG⁰ = 0 kJmol⁻¹ for O₂; [8].

Product	Reaction	Market price (€t ⁻¹)	Δ _f G ⁰ (kJmol ⁻¹) [8]	ΔW (kJmol ⁻¹)	Product molar mass, m (g) [8]	Electricity cost (€t ⁻¹)	CO ₂ DAC electricity cost (€t ⁻¹)
Methanol (CH ₃ OH)	2CO ₂ (g)+4H ₂ O(l) → 2CH ₃ OH(l)+3O ₂ (g)	555 [9]	-166.27	702.47	32.04	214	6.7
Ethylene (C ₂ H ₄)	2CO ₂ (g)+2H ₂ O(l) → C ₂ H ₄ (g)+3O ₂ (g)	1235 [10]	-68.15	1194.95	27.05	431	15.8
Methane (CH ₄)	CO ₂ (g)+2H ₂ O(l) → CH ₄ (g)+2O ₂ (g)	439 [11]	-50.72	808.02	16.04	496	13.3

Fig. 1. Representation of an electrochemical process for converting CO₂ selectively into methanol (CH₃OH). The process involves 12 electrons in order to convert 2 molecules of CO₂ and 4 molecules of water into 2 molecules of methanol releasing 3 molecules of oxygen. W-FDH: Tungsten-formate dehydrogenase; FDH: Formaldehyde dehydrogenase; MDH: methanol dehydrogenase.

Fig. 2. Representation of the electrochemical process proposed by Wang et al. [4] for direct air capture. The process involves 4 electrons for capturing 4 CO₂ molecules when KHCO₃ is formed and 3 CO₂ molecules when K₂CO₃ is formed.

Obtaining 1 t of methanol, instead of 1 mol (32.04 g) would therefore demand 21.9 GJ or 6.1 MWh. Market photovoltaic module efficiency in the range of 21 % efficiency has allowed a levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) in the range of 35 €MWh⁻¹ for crystalline silicon utility scale solar [12]. Assuming this price, 6.1 MWh of PV electricity would cost 214€. Since methanol market price is 555 €t⁻¹ [9] we find out that “thermodynamics” does not forbid the production of methanol from CO₂ and H₂O below current market prices and allows a margin of 341 €t⁻¹ to be spent in non-idealities of the system as well as CAPEX and OPEX costs.

Table I illustrates the results of the calculation above for the case of ethylene (resulting in a “thermodynamic” minimal cost of 431 €t⁻¹ vs 1235 €t⁻¹ market cost) and methane or natural gas (resulting in a “thermodynamic” minimal cost of 496 €t⁻¹ vs 435 €t⁻¹ market cost). As we can see, for the case of natural gas, this simple thermodynamic analysis allows to conclude that, with present costs, it would not be possible to produce CH₄ as solar fuel at competitive prices.

It is also possible to use thermodynamics to calculate the minimum amount of energy required to extract 1 t of CO₂ that is initially diluted in the atmosphere. To do so, it will be necessary to clearly specify what our initial and final thermodynamic states are (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Representation of a Direct Air Capture (DAC) process. All systems are at pressure p and temperature T .

We shall consider that our initial state corresponds to system 0, consisting of a volume of air V_0 , in standard conditions (defined by the pressure p and temperature T) and containing 1 t of CO₂ among all its molecules. Specifically, we shall consider that the system contains N_{CO_2} mol of CO₂ and a total of N_R mol corresponding to the remaining gases existing in air (oxygen, nitrogen, argon...). Along these calculations we shall assume all gases involved are ideal. Therefore, the volume V_0 , must verify that:

$$V_0 = \frac{(N_R + N_{CO_2})RT}{p} \quad (14)$$

where $R=8.21 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3\text{atmK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1} = 8.31 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kJmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ is the Richardson’s constant. In summary, system 0 corresponds to a volume V_0 of air before CO₂ is being extracted.

The explanation of these calculations will simplify if we calculate first the entropy S_0 of system 0, which is given by [7]:

$$S_0 = N_{CO_2} \frac{S_{0,CO_2}}{N_0} + N_{CO_2} R \ln \left(\frac{V_{CO_2,0}}{V_0} \frac{N_0}{N_{CO_2}} \right) + \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & N_R \frac{S_{0,R}}{N_0} + N_R R \ln \left(\frac{V_{R,0}}{V_0} \frac{N_0}{N_R} \right) \\ &= N_{CO_2} \frac{S_{0,CO_2}}{N_0} + N_{CO_2} R \ln \left(\frac{N_0}{N_{CO_2}} \right) + \\ & N_R \frac{S_{0,R}}{N_0} + N_R R \ln \left(\frac{N_0}{N_R} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where S_{0,CO_2} is the entropy of an amount of N_0 mol of CO₂ such that, when in standard conditions, they occupy the same volume V_0 given by Eq. (14), so that:

$$V_0 = \frac{N_0 RT}{p} = \frac{(N_R + N_{CO_2})RT}{p} \quad (16)$$

Hence, we have that:

$$N_0 = N_R + N_{CO_2} \quad (17)$$

as otherwise expected.

Similarly, $S_{0,R}$ is the entropy of N_0 mol of the rest of gases contained in air in standard conditions. Obviously, when considered ideal, this number of mols also occupy the volume V_0 since the pressure and temperature are the same.

The second equality in Eq. (14) comes from the fact that, in system 0, the molecules of CO₂ and the rest of molecules in air are mixed within the same volume so that they all initially share the same volume:

$$V_{CO_2,0} = V_{R,0} = V_0 \quad (18)$$

The final state (Fig. 3) consists of 2 systems. System 1 contains only the N_{CO_2} mol extracted from air in standard conditions. The volume of system 1, V_{CO_2} , is therefore given by:

$$V_{CO_2} = \frac{N_{CO_2} RT}{p} \quad (19)$$

System 2 consists of the original system 0 but from which CO₂ has been extracted. It occupies a new volume, V_R , given by:

$$V_R = \frac{N_R RT}{p} \quad (20)$$

The total entropy of system 1 plus system 2, S_f , is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} S_f &= N_{CO_2} \frac{S_{0,CO_2}}{N_0} + N_{CO_2} R \ln \left(\frac{V_{CO_2}}{V_0} \frac{N_0}{N_{CO_2}} \right) + \\ & N_R \frac{S_{0,R}}{N_0} + N_R R \ln \left(\frac{V_R}{V_0} \frac{N_0}{N_R} \right) = \\ & S_{0,CO_2} + S_{0,R} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

For the last equality in Eq. (21) we have used Eqs. (16), (17), (19) and (20). By subtracting Eq. (15) from Eq. (21) we obtain the increment in entropy, ΔS , corresponding to the ideal CO₂ direct air capture process from air:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S &= S_f - S_0 = \\ & -N_{CO_2} R \ln \left(\frac{N_0}{N_{CO_2}} \right) - N_R R \ln \left(\frac{N_0}{N_R} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Notice that, since $N_0 > N_{CO_2}$ and $N_0 > N_R$, the increase in

entropy is negative since the process we are analyzing corresponds to the unmixing of two gases. However, although there has been a decrease in entropy, the total internal energy remains constant ($\Delta U = 0$) that is, the internal energy of system 0 equals the internal energy of system 1 plus system 2. This is because, for ideal gasses, the internal energy only depends on the number of mols and the temperature [7] of the gas and none of these magnitudes have changed. Therefore:

$$0 = \Delta U = \Delta W - T\Delta S \rightarrow \Delta W = T\Delta S \quad (23)$$

where ΔW is the input work needed to decrease the entropy of the system and $T\Delta S$ the heat released from the system because of this decrease. We recall the heat released can be calculated as $T\Delta S$ because we assume the processes to be quasi-static and occur at constant temperature T .

Assuming 44.01 g CO₂ molar mass, we find that 1 t of pure CO₂ contains $N_{CO_2} = 22722$ mol. Also assuming CO₂ is concentrated in the atmosphere at 400 ppm (or, equivalently, 400 μ mol per mol) this leads to the fact that a total of $N_0 = 5.68 \times 10^7$ mol of air molecules are necessary to contain such amount of N_{CO_2} . Taking these numbers (together with Eq. (17), that can be approximated by $N_0 \approx N_R$, if desired) into Eqs.(22) and (23) we obtain, for $T = 298$ K, that a minimum of $\Delta W = 496.7 \times 10^3$ kJ (or 137.98 kWh) are necessary to extract 1 t of CO₂ from air. This corresponds also to a figure of 22 kJmol⁻¹ as thermodynamic limit to be compared with 400 kJ/mol reported experimentally by Wang et al. in their actual experiment.

Assuming a photovoltaic LCOE of 35 €MWh^{-1} , this translates into a cost of 4.8 € per t of CO₂ captured. This cost has been included in Table I under the heading “DAC cost” and expressed as per t of solar fuel sensitized. From this result we conclude that, from a thermodynamic point view, DAC does not introduce a prohibitive energy cost into the process.

Finally, for illustrative purposes we shall mention that the volume of air, V_0 , Eq. (14), required to contain 1 t of CO₂ is 1.8×10^6 m³, corresponding to a cube with a side of 111 m; the resulting volume, V_{CO_2} , Eq. (19), necessary to contain 1 t of CO₂ in standard conditions is 556 m³, resulting in a cube of 8.2 m side. 1 t of CO₂ is approximately the emissions that corresponds to two persons flying from Madrid to this Conference, in Milan, and return [13].

5 SUMMARY

The electrochemical processes for producing solar fuels from CO₂ are more complex than the ones involved in water electrolysis. Nevertheless, they are possible, and in this work we have described in detail one possible process, based on the use of several dehydrogenases, leading to the production of methanol. Moreover, electrochemical processes for direct CO₂ capture from air are also possible and, in this respect, we have reviewed the process described by Wang et al., based on the use of K₂SO₄ and ion selective permeable membranes which is compatible with the simultaneous production of hydrogen.

We have also described the fundamental thermodynamic analysis that allows to calculate the minimum amount of energy needed to carry out the processes and translate this energy into electricity cost. Assuming photovoltaic LCOE of 35 €MWh^{-1} , the

minimum cost for producing 1 t of methanol would be 214 € . Comparing this cost with methanol market price (555 €t^{-1}) this result still gives room for extra costs. The analysis of the ethylene is also favorable (431 €t^{-1} vs market price of 1235 €t^{-1}). However, the case of methane results unfavorable (496 €t^{-1} vs market price of 439 €t^{-1}).

The minimum cost of the energy needed for capturing 1 t of CO₂ from air has also been calculated from fundamental principles resulting in 4.8 €t that translates into a range of 6-14 € per t of solar fuel produced since each solar fuel demands a different amount of CO₂ to be produced.

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